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FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HYDROGEL CONTAINING AZITHROMYCIN AND SILVER NANOPARTICLES

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ABSTRACT

The main aim of the study is to formulate and evaluate hydrogel containing azithromycin and silver nanoparticles to treat wound dressing, burn infections, acne, Pharyngitis and Tonsillitis, psoriasis, etc. The Silver nanoparticles were prepared by green synthesis approach with the help of reduction of silver nitrate by Azadirachta indica leaves extract. Azithromycin was chosen as antimicrobial drug, however it shows adverse effect when administered in high dose, hence to reduce dose of azithromycin it was decided to make formulation containing silver nanoparticles and azithromycin. The drug loading and drug delivery techniques were searched for topical as well as bone grafting purpose. Initially mixing of Silver nanoparticles, Azithromycin and Bis acrylamide in ammonium persulphate were done and added N, N dimethyl amino ethyl methacrylate (DEM) to form semisolid mass that is hydrogel. Hydrogel formulation was found fantastic results with azithromycin and silver nanoparticles. The compatibility study was done for silver nanoparticles with polymer and azithromycin and all are found compatible with each other. All the formulations were characterized for consistency, spreadability, efficacy, safety and stability. From all F1-F12 Hydrogel Formulations F4 batch was optimized by parameters like pH measurement, spreadability, Drug content, Drug release and antimicrobial assay. So F4 batch was further evaluated for SEM, XRD, FTIR, skin Irritation study and showed good results. Hydrogel formulation of azithromycin and silver nanoparticles formulated for Azithromycin as a antimicrobial drug, however it shows adverse effect when administered in high dose, hence to reduce dose of azithromycin it was decided to make formulation containing silver nanoparticles and azithromycin. It was concluded that formulation was compatible with animal as well as human being with excellent evaluation results.

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INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology is a latest field of modern research. Nanotechnology has gained tremendous importance in state of the art techniques. Nanoparticles present a higher surface to volume ratio with their decreasing size. Currently, silver nanotechnology, is becoming popular due to its extensive applications and distinctive properties. There is an increasing demand for green synthesis which involves environmental friendly methods to synthesize nanoparticles.

In the present scenario, there is a growing interest in biological reduction of metal ions into metal nanoparticles. Elemental silver is considered to be very effective antimicrobial agent. The bioreduction of AgNO₃ using *Azadirachta indica* (Neem) leaves plant extract was implemented in this study. Drug delivery technologies play a vital role in pharmaceutical industry. Hydrogels are suitable for a variety of applications in the pharmaceutical and medical field. Hydrogels are characterized parameters like pH measurement, Spreadability, Viscosity, Skin irritation test, Drug release study, Drug content, etc. Nanoparticles have a great interest due to their extremely small size and large surface to volume ratio, which lead to both chemical and physical differences in their properties compared to bulk of the same chemical composition.

The main objective of research is that to formulate cost effective antimicrobial formulation for topical use which having excellent bioavailability

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Silver nitrate were purchased from Yogi Dye Chem industries, Mumbai for the synthesis of silver nanoparticles and azithromycin drug were received as gift sample from R.K. Universal Pharma, Mumbai. Excipients like Bis acrylamide, N, N'-dimethyl amino ethyl methacrylate, Ammonium Persulphate

Methods:

Preparation of silver nanoparticles:

The leaves were washed with distilled water and then dried in the shade for ten days. After that, the leaves were milled to obtain fine powders. Subsequently, 2 g of powders were mixed in a beaker with 100 ml distilled water and heated at 80 °C for 30 min, with magnetic stirring. Finally, the extract was filtered with Whatman filter paper # 1. The nanoparticles synthesis reaction consisted of the mix of 10 ml of AgNO₃ solution with the plant extract. The extract amount was varied using 2, 3, 4 and 5 ml and consequently changing the precursor salt-reducing agent relationship. In all cases, the reactions were carried out at room temperature and without magnetic agitation.

Evaluation of silver nanoparticles:

Motic microscopy:

Silver nanosuspension(5mM/ml) were taken and visualized under Motic microscopy for the determination of particle size of silver nanoparticles.

XRD analysis:

The phase variety and grain size of synthesized Silver nanoparticles was determined by X-ray diffraction spectroscopy (Philips PAN analytical). The synthesized silver nanoparticles were studied with CuK α radiation at voltage of 30 kV and current of 20 MA with scan rate of 0.030/s. Different phases present in the synthesized samples were determined by X'pert high score software with search and match facility. The particle size of the prepared samples were determined by using Scherrer's equation as follows $D \approx 0.9 \lambda \beta \cos \theta$ Where D is the crystal size, λ is the wavelength of X-ray, θ is the Bragg's angle in radians and B is the full width at half maximum of the peak in radians.

SEM analysis:

The morphological features of synthesized silver nanoparticles from neem plant extract were studied by Scanning Electron Microscope (JSM-6480 LV). After 24Hrs. of the addition of AgNO₃ the SEM slides were prepared by making a smear of the solutions on slides. A thin layer of platinum was coated to make the samples conductive. Then the samples were characterized in the SEM at an accelerating voltage of 20 KV.

Preparation of hydrogel containing drug and silver nanoparticles

Preparation of hydrogel base:

Gels were prepared by heating two thirds of the total amount of freshly prepared distilled water to 80 °C and then adding the required amount of polymer for dispersion. Following the addition of the required amount of plasticizer, the gels were thoroughly mixed. Cold water was then added to bring gels up to weight. The gels were triturated for 1 h to a uniform consistency and left overnight to equilibrate. Gels were centrifuged at 500 rpm for 20 min, and were then poured into special glass vessels (10 x 10 cm²).

Addition of drug and silver nanoparticles to hydrogel base:

As mentioned previously (preparation of hydrogel base), in prepared hydrogel base, different amounts of antimicrobial drug and specific quantity of silver nanoparticles (5mM and 10 mM concentration of AgNO₃) were added to the bases and then final weight of each base was adjusted by the addition of distilled water. The prepared suspension was blended for 1 h with mechanical blender, and centrifuged at 500 rpm for 20 min. It was then placed in a refrigerator for 24 h, for the emergence of bubbles and polymer swelling.

Table No.1: Composition of different Hydrogel formulations(F1-F6).

Sr. No	Drug/exciepient	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
1	Azithromycin	50 mg	50 mg	50mg	50mg	150mg	150mg
2	Silver Nanoparticle	5ml of	5 ml of	5ml of	5 ml of	5ml of	5 ml of
		5 Mm	5mM	10mM	10mM	5 mM	5 mM
3	Ammonium persulphate	2 ml	3 ml	2 ml	3 ml	2 ml	3 ml
4	BIS acrylamide	3ml	3ml	3ml	3ml	3 ml	3 ml
5	DEM	2ml	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml	2 ml

Table No.2: Composition of different Hydrogel formulations(F7-F12).

Sr. No	Drug/exciepient	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
1	Azithromycin	150mg	150mg	250 mg	250mg	250mg	250mg
2	Silver Nanoparticle	5ml of	5 ml of	5ml of	5ml of	5ml of	5ml of
		10mM	10 mM	5 mM	5mM	10mM	10mM
3	Ammonium persulphate	2 ml	3 ml	2 ml	3 ml	2 ml	3 ml
4	BIS acrylamide	3ml	3ml	3ml	3ml	3ml	3ml
5	DEM	2ml	2ml	2ml	2ml	2ml	2ml

Optimization of hydrogel containing azithromycin and silver nanoparticles:

PH determination:

2.5 gm of gel was accurately weighed & dispersed in 25 ml of purified water. The pH of the dispersion was measured using pH meter.

Drug content studies:

1.0 gm of each gel formulation were taken in 100 ml of volumetric flask containing 20 ml of phosphate buffer saline (pH 6.5) and stirred for 30 minute. The volume was made upto 100 ml & 1ml of the above solution was further diluted to 50 ml with phosphate buffer saline (pH 6.5). The resultant solution was filtered through membrane filter. The absorbance was recorded by using UV spectrophotometer at respective absorption maxima of Azithromycin & Silver nanoparticles i.e. 240 nm & 325 nm respectively. Drug content was determined from the calibration curve.

Spreadability:

It indicates the extent of area to which gel readily spreads on application to skin or affected part. The therapeutic potency of a formulation also depends upon its spreading value. Spreadability is expressed in terms of time in seconds taken by two slides to slip off from gel which is placed in between the slides under the direction of certain load. Lesser the time taken for the separation of two slides, better the spreadability. It is calculated by using following formula,

$$S = M. L / T$$

Where,

M = wt. tied to upper slide

L = length of glass slides

T = time taken to separate the slides [37].

In vitro permeation study of prepared gel:

In vitro release studies were carried out using Franz diffusion cell with receptor compartment having volume of 25 ml & an effective area of 2.54 cm². Receptor solution composed of distilled water. Phosphate buffer saline (pH 6.5) was added to the cell & temperature was maintained at 37±0.50 C and solution was stirred continuously at 600 rpm. Onion cell membrane was mounted on the receptor compartment with slide facing donor compartment. The donor compartment was filled with 200 mg of prepared gel. At appropriate time intervals of 1, 2, 3,5,6,7 & 8 hrs, 5 ml of sample were withdrawn & immediately replaced by equal amount of receptor solution. The sample were analysed by UV spectrophotometer at respective absorbance maxima of 325 nm & 240 nm.

Antibacterial activity:

The antibacterial activity of hydrogel nanocomposites was carried out against one Gram -ve bacteria (*E. coli*) and against one Gram +ve bacteria (*B. subtilis*) using disc plate technique. The nutrient broth agar was used for *B. Subtilis* and Meckonkii agar was used for *E. coli* bacterial species. Briefly, 500 μ l of bacterial suspension was added on the hydrogel sample (diameter: 1 cm, thickness: 2mm) contained in a 24well plate; the plate was subsequently incubated aerobically at 37 °C for 1 h; the microbial suspension was then removed and the gel rinsed three times with sterile PBS. 500 μ l of BHI diluted with PBS (1:10) was added in the well and the plate incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. An aliquot (50 μ l) from each well was transferred in a 100 well plate

Characterization of optimized formulation of hydrogel containing azithromycin and silver nanoparticles**Fourier Transform-Infrared Spectroscopy:** [30, 40, 41, 42, 43]

Drug-polymer interactions were studied by FTIR spectroscopy. The IR spectrum of optimized hydrogel containing azithromycin and silver nanoparticles compact were recorded. The spectrum was scanned over wavelength region of 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} to see the any interaction after formulation. FTIR spectrum of was determined by Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer. (Shimadzu, Japan). Sample preparation is done by making KBr (Potassium bromide) pellets and kept in beam of IR light and spectrum was recorded.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC): [37, 40]

DSC was performed in order to assess the thermotropic properties and thermal behaviour of the pure hydrogel and optimized formulation. The physical state of drug in the optimized hydrogel containing silver nanoparticles and Azithromycin compact was analysed by DSC. About 1 mg of the sample were sealed in aluminum pan and heated at the rate of 10⁰C/min, covering temperature range of 30 to 300⁰C under nitrogen atmosphere of flow rate 20 ml/min (PerkinElmer 4000).

X-Ray Diffractometry (XRD): [15, 37, 38, 40]

For characterization of crystalline state, the X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns for optimized Hydrogel containing azithromycin and silver nanoparticles compact prepared were determined using X-ray diffractometer (Bruker D8 Advance). The X-ray light were focused on the sample of hydrogel containing azithromycin and silver nanoparticles and diffracted light were recorded.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (sem): [15]

SEM was utilized in order to assess the morphological characteristics of the drug Azithromycin and optimized Azithromycin, silver nanoparticle containing hydrogel compact using a Field emission scanning electron microscope make- FEI (Nova Nano SEM 450).

The hydrogel containing silver nanoparticles were dried and mounted on a sample holder with the help of conductive tape accompanied by conductive metal such as platinum coating with a sputter coater. Finally focused beam of electrons on the sample and scanned. The image of the surface morphology is acquired from the secondary electrons effused from model surface detector.

Skin irritation studies:

The skin irritation study was done on Guinea skin for the purpose to check irritation for human skin. Guinea pigs (400-500 g) of either sex were used for testing of skin irritation. The animals were maintained on standard animal feed and had free access to water. The animals were kept under standard conditions. Hair was shaved from back of guinea pigs and area of 4 cm^2 was marked on both the sides, one side served as control while the other side was test gel was applied (500 mg / guinea pig) twice a day for 7 days.

RESULT & DISCUSSION**Characterization silver nanoparticles:****FTIR Spectroscopy:**

Table No.3: Peaks of FTIR of chemical group present in Pure Silver Nanoparticles.

Chemical group	Observed wave number(cm^{-1})
O-H group	3650
Secondary amine	1720
Protein	1539
Flavones	1391
Terpenoids	675

-X-RAY DIFFRACTION (P-XRD):

Polymorphic changes of drug are important factor which might affect the dissolution rate and in turn bioavailability. It is necessary to study polymorphic changes of the drug. Characterization of the crystalline state, the X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns is determined for drug, excipients used in formulation, physical mixture of drug and excipients, finally for the prepared hydrogel. Absence of constructive specific peaks of the drug in the hydrogel X-ray diffractograms indicate that drug has almost entirely converted from crystalline to amorphous or solubilized form. XRD spectrum showed distinct diffraction peaks around 38° , which are indexed by the (100) of the cubic face-centered silver and the sharp peaks indicates stabilized silver nanoparticles and broader peaks signify smaller particle size and reflect the effect due to experimental condition on the nucleation and the growth of the crystal nuclei.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM):

SEM analysis provided further detailed insight into the morphology and size details of the silver nanoparticles. Our experiments results showed that the size of synthesized nanoparticles in the colloidal solution ranges from 161-283 nm. [Fig. No. 7] showed nanoparticles at size 161 nm, 169 nm, 280 nm, 283 nm. Particles observed are predominantly spherical in shape and they are quite well distributed without any agglomeration. The synthesized nanoparticles were well stabilized by capping agent (plant phytochemicals) hence they were not in direct contact even within the aggregates as seen in SEM image Since these phytochemicals are involved in bonding with nanoparticles they provide charge to the nanoparticle. Repulsion due to the same charges between the particles keeps them from getting clumped together.

Motic Microscopy:

Particle size of pure silver nanoparticles were analyzed by Motic Microscopy and it was noted the result in different sizes like 0.1 μm and 0.3 μm . Hence it confirms that synthesized silver particles are in the nano range.

Compatibility Studies:

Fourier Transform-Infrared Spectroscopy:

The absorption peak was observed at 3437.16 indicates pure silver nanoparticles. The peaks at 3023.10 and 2991.50 are representative of C-H stretching. Absorption peak at 1710.86 indicates carbonyl (-C=O) bond stretching. A peak observed at 1402.25 is due to C-H bending and 674.73 due to terpenoids groups. The study concluded that no interaction were observed between Silver nanoparticles and polymer and further formulation were started on the basis of compatibility study.

Fig.9: FTIR spectrum of physical mixture of Silver nanoparticles, Azithromycin and Polymers.

Optimization of hydrogel containing silver nanoparticles & azithromycin:

Batches	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12
pH Measurement	5.0	5.0	5.1	5.5	5.0	5.4	5.5	4.8	4.9	5.1	5.1	5.3
Spreadability study	10.60	10.60	14.85	18.56	13.5	14.85	14.85	14.85	13.5	18.56	16.87	18.56
Drug release study (avg % drug release)	71.86	79.9	80.3	96.5	89.5	76.9	55.8	56.2	38.9	59.5	72.6	79.5
Drug content study	90.1	89.2	84.6	96.5	91.6	92.5	88.9	90.2	78.5	84.3	80.2	71.6
Wavelength Scan	440nm	420nm, 230nm	420nm, 230nm	410nm, 240nm	420nm	460nm	430nm, 230nm	450nm, 240nm	450nm, 230nm	450nm, 230nm	450nm, 220nm	450nm, 230nm.
Antimicrobial assay (E.coli) [in cm]	2.96	2.93	3.16	3.4	3.1	2.76	2.93	2.86	3.5	3.36	3.3	3.2
(B.subtilus)	3.33	3.13	3.36	3.46	3.16	3.23	3.0	3.4	3.4	3.26	3.23	3.33

Evaluation of optimized hydrogel containing silver nanoparticles & azithromycin

FTIR analysis was recorded on a Perkin Elmer Bx 11-FTIR Spectrophotometer, using the potassium bromide disk technique, in the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} . The disk was prepared from grinded samples (2 mg) and KBr (45 mg) using 400 kg/cm pressure for 10 min.

FTIR spectra of hydrogel. Examination of the spectra reveals various absorption peaks corresponding to chemical structure of bonds. The absorption peak was observed at 3437.16 which indicates that silver nanoparticles might be well bonded to the acrylamide gel during synthesis procedure. The peaks at 3023.10 and 2991.50 are representative of C-H stretching. Absorption peak at 1710.86 indicates carbonyl (-C=O) bond stretching. A peak observed at 1402.25 is due to C-H bending and 674.73 due to terpenoids groups.

Scanning Electronic Microscopy

A three-dimensional network structure is crucial to absorbing and keeping large amount of water in hydrogel materials. We examined the surface and cross-sectional morphologies of Ag-Az/BIS-DEM composite hydrogels by SEM. As shown in [Fig No.11], porous surface morphology and three-dimensional network structure in the cross section are formed in both BIS-DEM and Ag-AZ/BIS acrylamide-DEM hydrogels. No serious aggregation of the nanoparticles is observed even when the silver content is added. This can be explained as a stable network structure formed in the hydrogels and the strong interaction between the silver particles and the DEM and BIS acrylamide molecules. The size and distribution of silver nanoparticles in the gel matrix was studied by scanning electron microscopy, and the micrograph of gel -AgNP-Azithromycin is shown in [Fig.No. The presence of finely dispersed silver nanoparticles throughout the gel matrix is clearly seen. The average size of the silver nanoparticles is in the range 161–283 nm as calculated from the micrograph.

The porous morphology of the gel network and the presence of charged monomer units along the Co-polymer chain are believed to be the factors in stabilizing the silver nanoparticles against aggregation. Such domains of nanometer length scale allow the growth of silver nanoparticles. The porosity of gel network and hydrophilicity of polymer chain allow easy diffusion of small molecules (silver nitrate, sodium borohydride, and water) into the network for rapid reduction. The hydrogels facilitate easy diffusion of small ions for complexation and subsequent chemical reduction and these important properties are widely accepted in sensor technology and catalysis. The immobilization of silver nanoparticles throughout the hydrogel matrix is due to strong location of silver ions in the network. This is possible due to complexation of silver ions with nitrogen and oxygen atoms of the polymer chain.

Gels with high crosslinker content are rigid and restrict diffusion of ions leading to non-uniform distribution of nanoparticles in the gel matrix.

DSC Analysis:

From the result it was noted that acrylamide Hydrogel containing silver nanoparticles shown high thermal stability because high water loss shown by formulation F4 because of silver nanoparticles.

X-Ray Diffraction:

The XRD pattern of hydrogel was used to evaluate the nanoparticles formation in the gel networks. Hydrogel containing Azithromycin and silver nanoparticles have exhibited three sharp peaks in XRD. The sharp peaks are observed at 37.4, 44.69, and 64.38 h. The sharp peak at 37.4 indicates crystalline nature of silver nanoparticles. The peak at 44.69 indicates linkage between acrylamide and silver nanoparticles.

These three diffraction peaks in the XRD patterns at angles 37.4, 44.69 and 64.38 h are ascribed to Bragg reflections through (111), (200), (220) planes of the face-centered cubic packing of silver nanoparticles, respectively. However, these peaks are due to the formation of metallic silver nanoparticles in the gel networks.

Skin Irritation Studies:

The skin irritation study was done on Guinea pig skin to check skin irritation for human.

Photos of first day and 7th day were collected and compared. The results indicated that plain Azithromycin shown redness and sensitivity after 7 days was graded as 0, 1, 2, 3 for reaction, slight patchy erythema, but hydrogel containing silver nanoparticles does not showing any sensitivity as well as erythema and severe erythema with or without edema, respectively.

CONCLUSION

Silver nanoparticles were reported to have good antimicrobial activity in lower concentration and can combine with other antimicrobial agent to get synergistic effect. Hydrogel was formulated and was found fantastic results with azithromycin and silver nanoparticles. The compatibility study was done and silver nanoparticles with polymer and azithromycin found compatible with each other. From all F1-F12 Hydrogel Formulations, F4 batch was optimized by various parameters and showed good results. From the results it was concluded that the optimized hydrogel formulation will be used to treat wound dressing, burn infections, acne, pharyngitis and tonsillitis, psoriasis, etc.

The future work is to conduct formulation consumer attractable form as well as to check other effects this formulation on animals.

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